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BRANDING WITHIN THE SCOPE OF DESTINATION MARKETING:**HALLUM EXAMPLE**

DESTİNASYON PAZARLAMASI KAPSAMINDA MARKALAŞMA:

HELLİM ÖRNEĞİ

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In recent years, Geographical Indications have become a very important concept in commercial life and the consumer market. This concept, which is a tool of destination marketing, has perhaps become one of the indispensable parts of marketing in the developing and changing world. However, Geographical Indications are essentially a branding element and are also used as a marketing tool with the effect of branding. In this context, the concept of brand is important for cities and even countries as well as products and services. Because branding enables destinations to be distinguished from their competitors both within the country and abroad.

Products with a specific geographical indication are more advantageous than products with the same characteristics in terms of marketing and branding because they are trusted and preferred by the target audience and have a special market of their own. In this study, the principles of creating a destination brand, which is an important tool in destination marketing, were addressed and the aspects of Halloumi as a destination brand were examined.

Keywords : Trademark, Branding, Geographical Indications, Destination Marketing, Halloumi

ÖZ

Son yıllarda Coğrafi İşaretler, ticaret hayatında ve tüketici pazarında oldukça önem arz eden bir kavram haline gelmeye başlamıştır. Destinasyon pazarlamasının bir aracı olan bu kavram, gelişen ve değişen dünyada pazarlamasının belki de vazgeçilmezlerinden biri olmuştur. Ancak coğrafi işaretler esasen bir markalama unsuru olup markalaşmanın da etkisiyle bir pazarlama aracı olarak da kullanılmaktadır. Bu kapsamda marka kavramı, ürün ve hizmetlerin yanı sıra şehirler hatta ülkeler için de önem arz etmektedir. Zira marka destinasyonların gerek ülke içinde gerekse ülke dışındaki rakiplerinden ayırt edilmesini sağlamaktadır.

Belirli bir coğrafi işaret taşıyan ürünler, hedef kitle tarafından güven duyulan, tercih edilen ve kendi içerisinde özel bir pazarı bulunması sebebiyle pazarlama ve markalaşma kapsamında aynı niteliklere göre daha avantajlıdır. Bu çalışmada destinasyon pazarlamasında önemli bir araç olan destinasyon markasının oluşturulma ilkelerine değinilerek, Hellim'in bir destinasyon markası hususları incelenmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Marka, Markalaşma, Coğrafi İşaret, Destinasyon Pazarlaması, Hellim

1. INTRODUCTION

After globalization, the borders between countries have disappeared and movement between cities and countries has become easier. As a result, cities and countries that are seen as destinations have entered into intense competition to attract more entrepreneurs, investors, local and foreigners. In recent years, destination branding is one of the most important tools used by destination (country, region, city, etc.) managers to differentiate their regions from their competitors and achieve sustainable competitive advantage.

Today, it is to reveal to consumers the real differences between the goods and services offered by a destination and those offered by another country/destination. Therefore, consumers have to make decisions based on their basic beliefs and prejudices about countries. Since a destination with a strong, positive and permanent brand can continue to operate with a healthy profit margin, it is also possible to achieve a greater brand value (Anholt, 2009).

In this study, the geographical indication registration of Halloumi, which is an example of branding in destination marketing, and its connection with Cyprus were examined.

2. LITERATURE

2.1. Destination

According to Coltman, destination, which literally means destination, place to go, is defined as places with different natural attractions and features that will be considered attractive (Coltman,1989). Buhalis defines the destination as the combination of all products, services and final experiences provided locally (Buhalis, 2000: 98). A destination can be seen as a complex product of the tourism industry that includes the region's climate, infrastructure and superstructure, services, natural and cultural characteristics (Kim, 2010: 340). According to these definitions, destination is all of the attractions, services, facilities, infrastructure, landscapes, culture, hospitality and food and beverage activities that require coordination between different actors.

Destinations, countries, regions, towns and other areas are major locations of tourist activities and where people spend most of their time (Medlik, 2003:165). Destination is defined as a geographical place where local and touristic communities live together, visited or attracted by people who travel abroad for various purposes (Öztürk, 2013: 3). According to Murphy, Pritchard and Smith, a destination can be seen as a mixture of individual products and experience opportunities that come together to create the total experience of the visited area (Murphy, Pritchard ve Smith, 2000: 44). Destination is considered the main motivating factor behind consumer decisions and expectations (Fletcher, Fyall, Gilbert ve Wanhill, 2008: 124).

2.2. Marketing Concept

Marketing, which is based on temporal and spatial dimensions that include various market conditions and periodic changes among consumers, is a dynamic action to persuade customers to buy a product (Gümüş, 2024). In the Turkish Language Association (TDK) Dictionary, marketing is defined as the whole of activities aimed at identifying, meeting and promoting market needs in order to improve the sales of a product, a service or a good (tdk.gov.tr, 2023). Hacıoğlu defines marketing as determining the needs and desires of consumers to be satisfied, introducing techniques that enable goods and services suitable for these needs to reach consumers from producers, and then creating new needs and purchasing desires in consumers (Hacıoğlu, 2008:3). Therefore, marketing is business activities that ensure the flow of goods and services from producer to consumer.

Buskirk defined marketing, which is a process related to the estimation and determination of consumer needs, as all studies that ensure the flow of goods and services from the producer to the consumer or user (Buskirk,1970). As can be understood from this definition, marketing; It can be defined as a process that includes pricing, marketing communication and distribution activities of products, services and ideas (finished goods). The American Marketing Association defines marketing as creating, promoting and delivering value for customers in the context of changing conditions; It is defined as a set of processes aimed at managing customer relationships for the benefit of the organization and its stakeholders (American Marketing Association, 2004). Marketing can be expressed as a management process in which the consumer has the option to choose or reject for a certain price, willingly and in the expectation of mutual benefit, in order to respond to the material and spiritual needs of the product, and finally, it continues from the product's idea stage to the transportation stage to the consumer.

Based on these definitions, marketing has always been an important determinant for companies. In the production period that dominated the global system after the industrial revolution, marketing methods were quite simple. During this period, companies were producing and selling the products that consumers needed. Therefore, during this period, the consumer did not have more than one choice; However, with the expansion of the product range as a result of globalization and the introduction of technology into human life, the consumer changed his position and became the one who chooses the product. As the consumer has become a preferred person, the marketing and persuasion strategies of companies have also changed and optimizing marketing costs has become the main board. As social and digital media have become a part of daily life for almost every person with the technological revolution, it has created a great opportunity for companies to communicate and promote their products directly to potential target groups.

2.3. Branding

With the economic and technological changes taking place today, the brand, which enables companies to distinguish the products and services they produce from their competitors, has the function of providing information about quality and trust to people in marketing. Brand is at the center of what consumers need and value. A trademark used to distinguish the products of a commercial or industrial organization from the products of other organizations (Gümüş, 2023:685), it is a name, term, sign, symbol or design, or a combination of these, that helps identify the goods and services of a company or group of companies and distinguish them from those of its competitors (Kotler, 2000:789). In other words, the brand; It is the most important key to determining the goods and services of a business or business group and distinguishing them from those of its competitors.

The most important development that brings brand names and branding to the agenda is the necessity of producers to maintain a certain control and effectiveness over trade and consumers. This requirement is directly related to the differentiation of the producer-consumer relationship as a result of the industrial revolution and a market structure dominated by wholesalers (Işın ve Gümüş, 2019: 13). David A. Aaker, known as the pioneer of brand theory, evaluated it as a comprehensive term that is a name, term, symbol, shape or a combination of these that identifies products or services or their sellers and helps to distinguish them from others (David A. Aaker, 1996:10). According to another definition, the brand is the past and future of a product, it gives identity and meaning to the product, and beyond that, it indirectly establishes an emotional bond between the business and the consumer (Kapferer, 1994:177). Brand is an important tool that serves the purposes of increasing the competitiveness of businesses and directing the preferences of consumers correctly. In fact, the brand is the target point of marketing and advertising activities that influence and shape the consumer and her purchasing thoughts and decisions, and also distinguish the products from each other. For this reason, brands are

important in economic life for producers and intermediaries as well as consumers. By revealing the difference between products, the brand allows the consumer to make healthy product choices. For this reason, brands are important in economic life for producers and intermediaries as well as consumers. The brand enables the consumer to make healthy product choices by revealing the difference between the products (Gümüş, 2024:161).

Brand in the Marketing Context is a whole, a communication tool that is distinguished by the values it has among other similar products in the market. It is used to achieve specific marketing purposes and is the key that enables consumers to choose among similar products or services in the market. It is the identity of the product and service, its sales name. According to Rajaram and Shelly, brand is a sign that businesses use to distinguish their products from other companies' products and to introduce their own products to people in the market during the transportation of products (Rajaram ve Shelly, 2012:102). As a result, another feature of the brand, apart from being recognizable, is its promise to offer additional values to the customer that its competitors do not offer. A strong brand is more demanded by the target audience. Because these brands create and enrich an emotional bond with the product or service by providing more quality assurance to customers.

2.4. Destination Marketing

It is very important for the effective positioning and marketing of destinations, which are places with different natural attractions and features that will be considered attractive to consumers (Echtner ve Ritchie, 1993). Destination marketing acts around strategic objectives such as protecting the long-term welfare of people living in the region, ensuring consumer satisfaction, increasing the profitability of local entrepreneurs and creating a sustainable balance between socio-cultural features and economic benefit (Buhalis, 2000:21). In this respect, destination marketing emphasizes strategic importance and shapes many different ways with this strategy.

The International Destination Marketing Organization has put forward a comprehensive framework on what process should be followed in the marketing research of a destination, utilizing the elements of the extended service marketing mix. In this context, in the extended service marketing mix, "distribution element" is defined as the whole of all elements that bring together supply and demand at the destination (Middleton and Midgley, 1997). The marketing elements corresponding to the product element are; It is discussed as defining the attractions of the destination and using the most effective image, identity or brand. In this context, the first step to take is to contact the primary target markets.

It is stated that by determining which visitor groups are interested in the brand created for the destination, in what way and how they can be reached, the target market segmentation can prevent wasted energy and resources, and make realistic evaluations easier (Kozak vd. 2004). The success of destination marketing research points to a holistic structure that requires cooperation and working together in harmony (Garcia, Gomez ve Molina, 2012). Particularly, the cooperation of stakeholders becomes more important in the marketing of special destinations consisting of a specific product or service group (Lei, Huibin ve Kostopoulou, 2014). It is not possible to be successful when this cooperation is not achieved (Alvarez-Sousa, 2018; Wang and Fesenmaier, 2007; Yang, 2012). At this point, societies have realized the necessity of the participation of all stakeholders in order for their destinations to survive in the competitive environment and attract the attention of visitors, and have concluded that participation cannot be achieved without destination management organizations (Gryszel, 2012).

2.5. Geographical Indications

The concept of geographical indication is to increase the economic value of local products and to examine in detail the connection between geographical features and local products. Geographical Indication, which is one of the intellectual and industrial property rights, appears as a broad concept that covers all kinds of products specific to that geography due to the natural and human conditions in a region. Geographical Indications are the best quality products that belong to a certain region or region, have a special quality, are more likely to be preferred than similar ones, and are identified with that geographical region. Geographical indications are signs given to natural products, agriculture, mining, handicrafts and industrial products that stand out with their distinctive features and are identified with the region where they are located

Turkish Patent and Trademark Office defines a geographical indication as a sign indicating a product identified with a region, region or country of origin due to its distinctive quality, reputation or other characteristics (Türk Patent ve Marka Kurumu, 2022). From this definition, any product, fruit, stone, mineral of a region may be different from those produced in other regions, or the carpet, rug, fabric, tile, etc. produced in a region. We can infer that he may have become famous for some reason. Using the name of that region on these products may be perceived by consumers as having different features than similar products. Consumers can choose products sold with the name of that region over other products of the same type with the confidence they feel in the name of that region.

Figure 1. Geographical Indication Elements

Geographical Indication application can be briefly evaluated as protecting a local product or value within the framework of certain laws (Şahin, 2013). The first use of geographical indication in the world, which is a relatively new concept for our country, was in the 20th century. It was first seen in France. The first international agreement regarding geographical indications is the 'Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property' dated 1883. Following the Paris Convention, the 'Madrid Agreement Concerning the Prevention of False or Deceptive Origin Indications', dated 14 April 1891, contained regulations only regarding false and misleading origin indications, unlike the Paris Convention, which contained provisions on different concepts related to Industrial Property Rights (Kızıltepe, 2005: 86-88). With the 'Lisbon Treaty on the Protection and International Registration of Origin Names' signed in 1958, the definitions of the concepts included in geographical indication were rearranged and it was aimed to protect the products through registration. With the 'Treaty on Trade-Related

Intellectual Property Rights' (TRIPs) dated 15 April 1994, it was aimed to adequately and effectively protect geographical indications, like other intellectual property rights, at the international level (Yıldız, 2008: 50). The identity and characteristics of the products are subject to some rules and regulations in the Paris Convention. Later, the concept of geographical indication is also encountered in the practices of the European Economic Community and the European Union that was formed afterwards. In Turkey, the first geographical indication application was initiated in 1995 with the Decree Law No. 555 and the registration authority was given to the Turkish Patent Institute.

Geographical Indication Registration is of great importance in terms of providing local products with economic, cultural and legal brand value, as well as being used as an important rural development tool. Among the structural changes desired to be made in Turkey in the process of harmonization with the European Union, the development of rural areas within the social and economic structure of Turkey is among the priority issues (Kan ve Gülçubuk, 2008).

Geographical Indication products; It is registered in three different ways: Name of Origin, Country Designation and Traditional Product name. Name of Origin; It is the name given to products that are unique to a region with determined geographical borders, originating from natural and human elements specific to the determined region, and whose production, processing and other stages are carried out within the determined region (Esen, 2016: 453). In other words, products produced and processed in a certain geographical region using certain technical information are evaluated under the name of origin (Cebeci ve Şen 2020: 199). In summary, the name of origin is used for products that bear direct traces of natural and human conditions within a certain geographical area, where all the qualities of a product belong to this area

The main feature of the products named as origin in this context is that they cannot be produced outside the region they belong to. To give an example of the name of origin, Ankara Mohair, Van Otlu Cheese, Hellim, Isparta Rose. The indication of origin is on a narrower scale than the concept of origin, and although it originates from that geography, it means that at least one of the production and processing stages belongs to that region. According to Esen, the Geographic Sign; It is the nomenclature used for products that are specific to a region whose geographical borders are determined, whose distinct characteristics are identified with the determined region, and whose production and processing stages are made within the borders of the determined region (Esen, 2016: 453). Products that differ from other products in terms of their physical, sensory, chemical and microbiological properties due to geographical conditions are evaluated under the name of Country Mark (Cebeci ve Şen 2020: 199). If we give an example of the origin sign, Bolu Zucchini, Adıyaman Besni Grape, Adana Mother and Daughter Soup and Ayancık Linen Cloth. Traditional Product Name is defined in Article 34 of the Civil Code No. 6769. Names that have been proven to have been used traditionally for at least thirty years to describe a product in the relevant market that is not within the scope of the name of origin or origin indication are defined as meeting at least one of the following conditions. It is defined as originating from a traditional production or processing method or traditional composition and being produced from traditional raw materials or materials (6769 S. SMK: 2016, 38). The traditional elements in question are; It must distinguish the product in question from similar goods in the same category and give it a "certain quality". These elements may be related to the physical, chemical, microbiological or structural properties of the product. However, it is not enough for the way the product is presented, such as its packaging, to be traditional. Similarly, although there is no element of tradition in the production elements of the product, the fact that the product has reached a certain reputation cannot ensure that it can be described as a traditional product name (Yıldız, 2018: 36). For example, Ayvalık Toast, Turkish Baklava,

Turkish Coffee, Yogurt and Turkish Delight are among the examples to be given to traditional names.

In order for geographical indication to be made, there must be a product. These product or products are divided into five categories in SMK No. 6769. Food, agriculture, mining, handicraft products and industrial products can benefit from geographical indication protection, provided that they comply with the definitions and conditions specified in the law (article, 33.1). The names that will not be registered are specified as plant species and varieties and animal breeds (article 35.1/c).

Figure 2. Turkish Patent and Trademark Office Name of Origin, Country of Origin and Traditional Product Name Emblems

Figure 3. EU Designation of Origin, Country of Origin Designation and Traditional Product Name Emblems

While only agricultural products are included in geographical indication in European Union countries, in Turkey it can be used to register food and beverages, natural stones, natural beauties, craft products, animal species, souvenirs and agricultural products in many different categories. The products included in the registration reflect the culture of the society to which they belong and provide an advantage in the promotion and marketing of the region (Doğanlı, 2020: 532). Therefore, geographical indications are defined by the Turkish Patent and Trademark Office as signs indicating a product that is identified with a region, area, region or country of origin due to its distinctive quality, reputation or other characteristics.

Real or legal persons who are the producers of the product, Consumer associations, Governorship, District Governorate, Chambers of Commerce and Industry, which are public institutions related to the subject and geographical region, have the right to apply for geographical indication (Türk Patent ve Marka Kurumu, 2022). Geographical indication can

be used by anyone who produces in accordance with the conditions set out in the registration. Those who want to apply for a geographical indication apply to the Geographical Indications Department of the Turkish Patent and Trademark Office. Geographical indications registered in Turkey are valid only within the borders of Türkiye. In case of protection abroad, an application must be made in each country in accordance with the country's legislation. On the other hand, a geographical indication obtained by consumer associations, Governorship, District Governorate, Chambers of Commerce and Industry, which are public institutions related to the subject and geographical region, can also be used by citizens/business people living in that region. A business owner or person who wants to use the geographical indication emblem in question must apply to the governor's office. If the governorship gives permission to use the geographical indication after inspecting the relevant place, the operator or citizen will be able to use this emblem on their products. There is no time limit in this procedure. The operator who wants to use the geographical indication emblem can apply to the governor's office at any time.

2.6. Destination Marketing and Brand Relationship

With globalization, destinations have started to pay more attention to the strategic marketing model. Economy is the main reason for destination branding. This concept, which has become widespread since the 1990s, aims to first make people aware of the destination through branding and then to create the desired associations regarding that destination. In branding, the aim is to present a positive and attractive image to the outside world while meeting the needs of the businesses and residents operating in the settlement (Kavaratzis ve Ashworth, 2008:160). Therefore, destination branding will enable destinations to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors by differentiating their goods and services (Rainisto ve Kotler, 2007:3). In other words, destination branding is the process of developing identity and personality that helps distinguish a destination from its competitors (Qu, Kim ve Im, 2011).

The conceptual framework developed by Hankinson defines destination branding as "relational brand networks" (Hankinson, 2004: 110). Destination branding is a logo, symbol, name, wordmark, or various graphics that differentiate the destination from others and is uniquely associated with it, supported by the promise of an unforgettable travel experience and enhancing recall (Ritchie ve Ritchie, 1998: 18). George, on the other hand, has adopted a more comprehensive approach to destination branding that includes issues such as differentiation, experience, expectations, image and reinforcement (George, 2017: 13). From these definitions, we can essentially express the destination brand as the element that includes marketing activities to support the logo, symbol, name and word brand that easily identifies and distinguishes a destination, and also strengthens the emotional connection between the visitor and the destination. _Krajnovic, define destination branding as the process of becoming a preferable tourist destination within or outside the country, as well as a region where economic development is hoped for and gaining a unique, competitive identity (Krajnovic vd., 2013: 5).

Destination branding can be defined as being a region where economic development is targeted and the process of gaining a unique and competitive identity (Krajnovic vd.,2013: 5). This type of branding has a different structure than traditional product and service branding and has a complex structure. In this context, an important step in destination branding is the ability to act jointly (Middleton, 2011: 17). Therefore, brands give identity to any destination and the brand becomes the symbol of the destination identity. The destination brand has argued that although its focus is on developing the destination identity, it is also about adding additional attractions to this identity (Rainisto, 2003:142). Destinations that want to survive in the competitive environment must make innovations for this purpose. When branding a destination, elements such as goods and services, art, investment, technology, education and tourism that make up the destination must be brought together under one roof (Rainisto, 2003:147).

It is easier to distinguish the branded destination from other destinations. Thus, it ensures the sustainability of the destination in a competitive environment. Destination branding ensures the quality and reliability of the product. Consumers turn to branded products because their risks are low. At the same time, purchasing activities are easier for consumers who establish an emotional bond with branded products. Effective destination branding begins with a clear understanding of the essence of a destination by clearly identifying its distinctive contextual attributes, such as attraction and service (Williams, 2004). By using input from various stakeholders in the branding process, it theoretically transforms the tangible and intangible characteristics of the destination into an identity so that it can be attractive in the market (Hall, 2002).

3. BRANDING WITHIN THE SCOPE OF DESTINATION MARKETING: HELLIM

3.1. Purpose of the Research:

The aim of this study is to examine the destination brand issues by touching on the principles of creating the destination brand, which is an important tool in the destination marketing of HELLIM, which has geographical indication as the source and origin of different cheese varieties in Turkey.

3.2. General Information Obtained About Halloumi and Its Distinctive Features

Turkish Language Association Dictionary of Turkish Dialects of Türkiye defines the meaning of the word hellim as "A kind of cheese." He states that this word is used in this sense in Adana as well as in Cyprus. Halloumi, Greek χαλούμι; Its Arabic name is حلوم, ḥallūm, and it is a fresh cheese of Cypriot origin, with a tight texture and yellowish white color. It is generally eaten after being grilled or fried in a pan without oil. Additionally, halloumi is an important export item of the Republic of Cyprus and Northern Cyprus (www. <https://tr.wikipedia.org>: access date : 28.10.2024).

Halloumi is produced and marketed in two types: fresh and ripe. Fresh Halloumi; It is the product obtained by adding rennet to milk and applying a halloumi-specific production method. Physical Characteristics: It has a double-layered, semicircular or rectangular structure and is white to light yellow in color. HELLIM, which is semi-hard and elastic, has a unique taste and smell. Chemical properties; maximum moisture percentage: 46%, minimum fat percentage: 43% on dry matter, salt percentage: 3% - 5%, maximum acidity: 3.5% on dry matter as lactic acid. To produce fresh halloumi and ripe halloumi, it is made from raw sheep-goat, sheep-goat-cow milk mixtures or separate sheep and goat milk. Juice taken from the fourth stomach of calves and rennin enzyme are used as rennet. Rennin enzyme has the ability to coagulate milk. Yeast obtained from pork sirloin is not used in the production of halloumi.

Milk used in making halloumi; It is raw or pasteurized Cypriot milk with a unique taste and aroma, resulting from the fact that all or most of the feed needs of dairy animals are met by forages produced from free pastures and native plants in Cyprus. It is not allowed to thicken the milk from which halloumi will be made, or to add milk powder or thickened milk, rock salt, colorants, preservatives or other additives. In addition, the presence of antibiotics, herbal medicines and other harmful chemicals in the milk used in halloumi production is prohibited. Sheep and goat milk is provided from local breed animals and hybrid animals adapted to the climatological conditions in Cyprus. To be more precise, sheep's milk is obtained from fat-tailed Cyprus native sheep and their offspring obtained as a result of crossbreeding these sheep with Sakız, Awassi and Ost-friesian breeds in line with various breeding programs.

The usage feature of halloumi is that it does not spread or melt when exposed to high temperatures. Due to this feature, it has the privilege of being consumed plain as well as cooked using pans, grills and similar methods. Halloumi is traditionally consumed with watermelon, in pasta, with soup, especially tarhana soup, and in pieces in various types of bread.

Şekil 4. Helim Peyniri

Production Method: Halloumi production in Cyprus has been known for centuries. Halloumi production and consumption is indispensable for every farmer family in Cyprus, and has a special importance because it not only meets the nutritional needs of families, but also creates the opportunity for social solidarity and cooperation between families. Halloumi is produced from raw or pasteurized sheep or goat milk or their mixture with cow milk. It is important that the milk used in halloumi production is obtained from healthy animals. Milk obtained after the 5th or 7th day following the birth of the animal and which has lost its colostrum feature, can be used in making halloumi. Colostrum milk cannot be used in making halloumi. Raw milk is kept under appropriate temperature conditions from milking to fermentation. It is not allowed to thicken the milk to be used in halloumi making, or to add milk powder, thickened milk, rock salt, colorants, preservatives and other additives. In addition, the presence of antibiotics, herbal medicines and other harmful substances in the milk used in halloumi production is prohibited. The milk produced within the borders of Cyprus is transported to halloumi production facilities with appropriate vehicles where raw milk quality is preserved and is stored under appropriate conditions in cold stores.

Halloumi production in the Republic of Cyprus has increased greatly in recent years. Halloumi, which holds a 27% share among the agricultural products exported by the country, is the agricultural product exported the most by the country. It is a popular type of cheese in the Middle East and wherever people of Cypriot origin live. "Geçitkale Halloumi Festival" has been organized by Geçitkale Municipality every year since 2008. Events such as "The Most Delicious Fresh Halloumi Competition" and "Hallum Beauty Contest" are organized in this festival. Today, many countries in the Middle East produce halloumi. Apart from this, halloumi, which is an industrial product, is available in grocery stores and some supermarkets owned by Turks, Greeks and Arabs in Germany.

3.3. Protection of HELLİM as a Geographical Indication in Turkey and the EU:

For a branded Geographical Indication product, its competitors must have experience. The region where the Geographical Indication registered product is located will be visited, there will be activity in the region and positive effects will begin to be seen in the development and development of the region. The concept of Geographical Indication Registration is an important value that promotes rural development and rural tourism by highlighting locality and local branding. It has created some cultural and economic opportunities for products that have received Geographical Indication Registration. The most important of these opportunities is to increase the recognition of the region and thus become an important destination in rural tourism with branded local products and generate economic income. The realization of social and economic expectations based on local products depends on paving the way for branding by obtaining geographical indication registration.

In this context, Halloumi, which is the subject of the research, is a registered name of origin in Turkey with the number C2008/046 by the Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Industry since 10.10.2008. It is carried out by the competent authority appointed by the Ministry of Agriculture within the administrative borders of the provinces of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. The audit report regarding the audits must be submitted to the Turkish Patent and Trademark Office every year by the registrant. Since there is no governorship in Cyprus, people/businesses who want to use this sign must apply to the Chamber of Commerce, not the governorship. If the Chamber of Commerce gives its approval to use the geographical indication after inspecting the relevant place, the operator or citizen can use this emblem on their products.

The Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Cyprus actually applied for registration of halloumi with the European Union under the name "Halloumi" in 2007. However, this application was rejected in July 2010. Subsequently, the Greek Cypriot Administration of Southern Cyprus applied to the European Commission to register the product Χαλλούμι/Halloumi/Hellim as a designation of origin (PDO) on 17 July 2014. Following the publication of the application in question, total of 17 objections were received from Dairy Australia and FFF Fine Foods Pty Ltd from Australia, Common Food Names Consortium (United States), United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, Dairy and Fat Products Production and Marketing Cooperative Ltd from the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. ., Animal Producers and Breeders Association, Fatma Garanti, Dairy Producers Association, Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Industry, Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Commerce, Navimar Food from Turkey. Manufacturing and Food, DM Foodstuffs Marketing Industry and Trade Ltd. Şti., Avunduk Import Export Food and Agricultural Equipment Industry Trade Ltd. Şti., UTCO Trading Company – WLL – (Kuwait) comprising the New Zealand Dairy Association and the New Zealand Specialist Cheese Producers Association (New Zealand) and Dr Nutrition (United Arab Emirates).

HELLİM, which is a rare example, has the same origin name registered by different people in the Greek and Turkish parts. Members of the European Commission describe this as a political and economic success. Members of the European Commission describe this as a political and economic success. Thus, it made it easier for consumers in the EU to get to know this product. The geographical limit of the name of origin in question is stated as the entire Turkish and Greek sides of the island of Cyprus. Therefore, halloumi constitutes the first form of trademarks as it identifies the origin of the product used. By preserving a certain quality of the product, it has become a national value.

4. CONCLUSION

The physical and geographical conditions of any country in the world directly affect human and economic life and enable many economic activities to be carried out. Therefore, it shapes human and economic life as much as geographical conditions allow. Geographically indicated products are economic activities that are important first for the agricultural economy and then for businesses in the market. Geographic products in this high-quality product class, which act as a locomotive, combine with the cultural values of that region and have a very high level of brand value and brand awareness among consumers in the final market. Geographic products in this high-quality product class, which act as a locomotive, combine with the cultural values of that region and have a very high level of brand value and brand awareness among consumers in the final market. This high brand awareness, after brand registration, not only provides more profitable sales returns with the increase in the price of that product, but also gives the opportunity to capture different markets in foreign markets with export marketing activities of that product. Branding of products with geographical indications serves as a kind of shield to prevent unfair competition or fake brands.

Recently, destination marketing has been focused on countries, regions, cities, etc. Promoting the regions within its borders is an important parameter to provide competitive advantage by differentiating them from others. For a destination to become a brand, its historical, geographical, cultural and economic characteristics have an important place. Because the branding of the destination creates trust for the consumer, arouses emotions and encourages and mobilizes the consumers. In this context, destination branding is primarily the creation and dissemination of a positive perception and image about the destination, which is similar to product branding, expresses that product and makes it distinctive compared to other products.

Geographically indicated products are important to make branding effective by strengthening the image of the destination. The richness of the traditional and local product potential in the destination contributes to regional development and leads to an increase in the welfare level of the local people. In this context, we can conclude that HELLİM, one of the important export items of Cyprus, is a destination brand. Although it is a very important point for Cyprus to be able to market and promote it to the world in the strongest possible way, the main point that must be taken into consideration for both consumers and producers is that the basic features of the product do not change so that the geographical indication can continue for generations. Because when Cyprus is mentioned, it is the first food product that comes to mind when it comes to eating and drinking.

We can also conclude that the protection process of halloumi, which has an important place for the citizens of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus and the Greek Republic of Southern Cyprus, continues in the most peaceful and constructive way. Considering the political situation of the island of Cyprus, it would be considered acceptable to encounter a very exceptional situation such as the same product being registered by different states in different geographies. However, considering the situation created by the duality in the management process of the Halloumi name of origin, especially among the producers, some responsibilities of the registrant have changed the addressee with the differentiation of geographies.

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